

Strategies for Sustainable Access to Safe and Clean Water of Purba Medinipur District, West Bengal

Paper Id : 20928 Submission Date : 2025-12-12 Acceptance Date : 2025-12-21 Publication Date : 2025-12-25

This is an open-access research paper/article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

DOI:10.5281/zenodo.18221156

For verification of this paper, please visit on <http://www.socialresearchfoundation.com/remarking.php#8>

Mahua Dutta

Assistant Professor
Department Of Geography
Gokhale Memorial Girls'
College
Kolkata W.B., India

Abstract

Access to safe and clean water is a critical prerequisite for public health and sustainable development. In Purba Medinipur district, West Bengal, groundwater is the dominant source of drinking water, making its quality and sustainable management a pressing concern. This study assesses the physico-chemical parameters of groundwater samples from multiple blocks, comparing them with BIS and WHO drinking water standards. Field surveys and stakeholder interviews were conducted to understand usage patterns, seasonal fluctuations, and community perceptions. Results indicate spatial variability in water quality, with issues such as salinity intrusion in coastal areas, iron and fluoride contamination in pockets, and declining water tables due to over-extraction. The findings highlight the urgent need for integrated strategies, including improved monitoring, aquifer recharge initiatives, policy enforcement, and community participation. Such measures are vital to achieving Sustainable Development Goal 6—ensuring equitable access to safe and clean water for all—while safeguarding groundwater for future generations.

Keywords

Safe Drinking Water, Groundwater Quality, Purba Medinipur, Salinity Intrusion, Iron Contamination, Fluoride, Over-Extraction, Sustainable Management, SDG 6, West Bengal.

Introduction

Ensuring access to safe and sufficient water for all is a critical concern in the context of sustainable development and the escalating challenges of global climate change. At the moment, around two billion people across the globe still lack access to clean drinking water, representing a significant hurdle for policymakers working towards achieving Sustainable Development Goal 6 (SDG-6), which aims to guarantee safe water for everyone by 2030.

In many developing countries, including India, numerous surface water bodies have become contaminated due to the discharge of untreated domestic sewage, harmful industrial waste, and dangerous agrochemicals, making them unfit for use without adequate treatment. Consequently, groundwater has become the primary source of water for drinking, agriculture, and industrial purposes in many parts of the nation, owing to its accessibility and natural resistance to microbial contamination. However, the quality and availability of groundwater are increasingly under threat due to several factors. These factors include over-extraction, rapid urban growth, industrial expansion, intensive farming, and more. Among the pollutants affecting groundwater, diverse inorganic substances, especially heavy metals, have emerged as major contributors. Even though some of these metals are essential in small quantities for human health, their excessive presence can lead to health risks.

One of the most severe examples of groundwater contamination is the presence of arsenic in the Bengal Basin, a densely populated region where millions have suffered due to what has been termed mass poisoning. Elevated arsenic levels were first discovered in shallow tube wells of the basin in the late 20th century.

Although South and Southeast Asia have experienced the most severe impact, arsenic contamination is a global issue. This naturally occurring element is widely distributed in the Earth's crust and has been detected in the air, soil, and water of more than 70 countries. In total, approximately 500 million people worldwide are believed to be exposed to unsafe levels of arsenic in drinking water, including populations in countries such as China, Argentina, Chile, Mexico, and the United States.

West Bengal, under the Jal Jeevan Mission (JJM), prioritizes the delivery of safe drinking water through piped supply systems, especially in regions affected by arsenic contamination. In the interim, the state has adopted community water purification plants (CWPPs) to provide clean water to vulnerable communities.

Study area:

The district of Purba Medinipur is situated between 21⁰ 38' north and 22⁰ 30' north latitude, and 87⁰ 27' east and 88⁰ 11' east longitudes. Purba Medinipur is bounded on the north by the district of Paschim Medinipur (Fig. 1), on the east by the river Rupnarayan – the tributary of Hugli. The river Hugli itself separates the district from Haora and South 24 Parganas. Its southern boundary is the coast line of Bay of Bengal.

Source: National atlas and Thematic Mapping Organization, 2017, Census of India, 20011.

Fig. 1

The district is bounded by Paschim Medinipur on the west and the south-western boundary merges with the state of Orissa. The district looks like a large open plain area composed of younger alluvium on the northern portion borne by river Hugli and its tributaries. Coastal alluvium stretches to the southern fringe facing the sea. The district slopes gradually from the north-west to the Contai littoral tracts of Bay of Bengal. The district looks like a large open plain area composed of younger alluvium on the northern portion borne by river Hugli and its tributaries. Coastal alluvium stretches to the southern fringe facing the sea. The major rivers are Rupnarayan and Hugli. The district is also traversed by the rivers like Kangsabati (Kasai), Kaliaghai, Rasulpur and Haldi. tract of Bay of Bengal. The major rivers are Rupnarayan and Hugli.

Objective of study

The primary objective of this study is to analyse the multilayered impact of a major developmental intervention of the rural community of Purba Medinipur district. Specific attention has been given to the amount of changes which influence social structure, cultural identity and livelihood pattern. It aims to investigate the nature and extent of resource uses, health conditions and inter community relations. Another objective is to critically analyse existing governmental policies, legal frameworks and protective measures to determine the extent and nature of safeguards and rights. The study also seeks to identify gaps in current approaches

Review of Literature

and propose more sustainable strategies that balance infrastructural development. The objective is also to encourage preparing development models balancing between ecological stability and long term survival of the local community.

Groundwater is a vital natural resource that is provided for drinking water supply, agriculture and other socio economic development most particularly in the developing countries like India. Rapid population growth, urbanisation, agricultural revolution and climatic variability have significantly increased dependence on underground water resulting in a growing stress on both their quality and quantity. Access to safe and clean drinking water is widely recognised as a fundamental requirement for public health and sustainable development and is explicitly addressed under Sustainable Development Goal 6. India is currently the largest extractor of groundwater in the world, according to nearly one-fourth of global groundwater withdrawal (Shah, 2009). Groundwater meets about 85% of rural drinking water requirements and plays a crucial role in irrigation based agriculture (Central Ground Water Board, 2022). Several studies have highlighted that unregulated abstraction, inadequate monitoring and weak institutional frameworks have resulted in widespread groundwater depletion across the country (Rodell et al., 2018). Alongside depletion, deterioration of groundwater quality has emerged as a serious challenge that directly threatens drinking water security and human well-being (MacDonald et al., 2016). West Bengal exhibits a complex hydrogeological setting comprising lateritic uplands in the west and extensive alluvial, deltaic and coastal aquifers in the east. Groundwater quality issues in the state have been extensively studied with particular emphasis on arsenic contamination in the Ganga - Brahmaputra delta (Bhattacharya et al., 2009; Chakraborti et al., 2015). While arsenic contamination remains a major concern, recent literature indicates that other physico-chemical problems such as iron, fluoride, salinity and nitrate contamination are increasingly affecting groundwater quality in several districts (Central Ground Water Board, 2020). Purba Medinipur district, located in the lower Gangetic delta along the Bay of Bengal is characterised by low lying topography, unconsolidated alluvial sediments and a dense network of tidal rivers and creeks. Studies have shown that excessive extraction of groundwater, combined with limited recharge has facilitated saline water intrusion in coastal aquifers, particularly in blocks such as Ramnagar I, Ramnagar II and Contai I (saha et al., 2018; Mukherjee et al., 2020). Climate change has further intensified groundwater related challenges in coastal West Bengal. Sea level rise, increased frequency of cyclonic storms and storm surges have contributed to the inland movement of saline water, thereby deteriorating freshwater aquifers (intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change, 2021). Monsoonal rainfall often improves groundwater quality through dilution and recharge, whereas pre-monsoon periods are marked by declining water tables and higher concentration of dissolved salts and contaminants (Kumar et al., 2020). Studies conducted coastal districts of West Bengal have reported that a significant proportion of groundwater samples exceed permissible limits prescribed by the Bureau of Indian Standards (IS 10500:2012) and the World Health Organization (WHO, 2017), particularly for iron, salinity and hardness (Das et al., 2017; Ghosh & Biswas, 2021). Recent studies emphasise that sustainable groundwater management requires more than technical solutions. Governance mechanisms, community participation and awareness play a critical role in ensuring long term water security (Meinzen-Dick, 2014; Mukherjee et al., 2019). In rural West Bengal, community perceptions of water quality are often based on taste, colour and availability rather than assessments, resulting in a gap between perceived and actual water safety. Groundwater quality has direct implications for public health and sustainable development. Long term consumption of contaminated groundwater has been associated with chronic health issues such as fluorosis, and gastrointestinal disorders (WHO, 2017). Achieving SDG 6 goal, therefore, requires integrated, region specific strategies encompassing scientific monitoring, aquifer recharge, policy enforcement and community involvement (UN-Water, 2023). Despite existing studies, comprehensive block level assessments, integrating physico-chemical analysis and socio environmental dimensions in Purba Medinipur district remains limited. The present study aims to address these gaps by adopting an integrated and sustainable approach.

Main Text

Arsenic Contamination in India

According to data collected by The World Bank, India has 18 % of the population of the world but only 4% of its water resources, which makes it one of the most water-stressed nations in the world. Arsenic contamination in India is a major public health and environmental concern. It impacts diverse regions across the nation. Arsenic is a naturally occurring element that can contaminate groundwater, thereby posing a variety of health risks when consumed over an extended period of time. Groundwater Arsenic contamination was first identified in India in 1983, as patients were reported from 3 families in a village of 24 Parganas district in West Bengal. Subsequent to that, a number of cases were

reported not only from Bengal, both other states like Jharkhand, Assam, Bihar, Uttar Pradesh, and more. Areas located in the Ganges-Brahmaputra delta region are the most severely impacted by arsenic contamination. The contamination is primarily found in groundwater sources, which many communities in India, especially in its rural areas, depend on for drinking water.

Causes of arsenic contamination in India can be broadly categorized under:

Natural Sources: In many cases, arsenic contamination in groundwater is result of geological processes, where arsenic naturally occurs in particular rock formations.

Human Activities: Even though natural sources do play an important role, discerning human activities like industrial processes, mining, as well as the use of arsenic-containing pesticides also majorly contribute to localized contamination

Discovery of extensive arsenic contamination in West Bengal's groundwater:

In the year of 1982, Kshitish Chandra Saha, a dermatologist working at the School of Tropical Medicine in Kolkata, India, encountered two patients exhibiting unusual dark skin patches. Initially, he believed the symptoms were indicative of leprosy, a disease still prevalent in India at the time. However, upon closer examination, Saha revised his diagnosis and attributed the condition to arsenicosis—arsenic poisoning. This insight proved to be a groundbreaking moment in public health, as it led to the identification of widespread arsenic contamination in the groundwater of West Bengal. In fact, the magnitude of this discovery was so significant that the World Health Organization (WHO) later classified it as the "greatest mass poisoning in human history."

The crisis of arsenic poisoning persists in West Bengal even after three decades. Current estimates suggest that approximately 90 million people in India and an additional 40 million in neighbouring Bangladesh are still consuming arsenic-laced drinking water.

Dealing with arsenic contamination doesn't necessarily require complex or high-cost technologies. Even having simple filtration systems in place, made of sand and iron nails, can effectively remove arsenic from water. The real problem lies in the practical implementation of these solutions. In remote, underdeveloped regions, especially those inhabited by impoverished communities, the widespread distribution and maintenance of such filters remain major obstacles. Moreover, the lack of funding and infrastructure has hindered large-scale testing efforts, especially in rural areas of West Bengal, making it difficult to map the full extent of arsenic spread.

Impact on agriculture

The Central Government has informed the National Green Tribunal (NGT) that West Bengal and Bihar are the states most severely affected by arsenic contamination in groundwater. This information was provided in response to the tribunal's inquiry into the vulnerability of rice crops to arsenic exposure, owing to their ability to absorb more of the toxic metalloid from both soil and water.

The Centre highlighted that groundwater used for irrigation is the primary pathway through which arsenic enters agricultural soil, eventually making its way into the food chain. As rice is a water-intensive crop, it is particularly prone to absorbing and accumulating arsenic, potentially leading to a significant build-up of the element in the grain. The risk is further magnified by the transport of contaminated rice from arsenic-affected areas to regions that are not naturally exposed, thereby increasing arsenic exposure among populations in non-endemic areas.

According to the Centre's response, the distribution of arsenic within plant tissues typically follows a pattern—starting with the roots, followed by stems and leaves. Edible parts of leafy vegetables such as spinach and fenugreek, as well as underground vegetables like beets and radishes, tend to accumulate higher levels of arsenic in comparison to fruit-bearing vegetables such as brinjal, beans, okra, and tomatoes. Generally, the fruit and grain portions of plants absorb less arsenic than the roots and foliage.

To mitigate the harmful effects of arsenic in the soil-plant system, the government proposed several remedial strategies. These include promoting less water-intensive crops in place of rice, cultivating arsenic-tolerant rice varieties, and planting leguminous or non-edible crops during the dry season in highly affected areas. The application of biochar, which is a charcoal derived from biomass, as

well as the use of green manure and silicate fertilizers, was also recommended to reduce arsenic absorption in crops. Moreover, the Centre suggested managing arsenic-laden groundwater by storing it in ponds, allowing for natural dilution with rainwater, and using a mix of surface and groundwater sources to reduce overall arsenic concentrations.

Health Impacts of Arsenic contamination

According to the World Health Organization (WHO) Chronic exposure to arsenic may cause skin problems as well as damage to the neurological and reproductive systems. It would increase the risk of cardiovascular problems, diabetes mellitus, respiratory and gastrointestinal diseases and cancer. Long-term intake of arsenic-contaminated water can lead to arsenic poisoning or arsenicosis, with cancer of the skin, bladder, kidney, or lung. Arsenicosis is a chronic health condition that is caused by prolonged ingestion of Arsenic above the safe dose for at least six months. This condition is typically manifested by characteristic skin lesions of melanosis and keratosis, which may occur alone or in combination, with or without the involvement of internal organs. Children, pregnant women, and people with pre-existing health conditions can be relatively more susceptible to the adverse health effects of arsenic exposure. Children are particularly vulnerable to Arsenic contamination. As their system tries to expel the poison, their internal organs can be affected severely, which may stunt their physical and mental growth. Unfortunately, there are still millions of children in India who drink the poisonous water from their school or village handpumps. Exposure to high concentrations of arsenic during pregnancy is also associated with an increased risk of miscarriages, stillbirths, preterm births, low birth weight as well as neonatal deaths.

Plate- 1

The main source of drinking water in the villages – tubewell, Kolaghat Block.

Table - 1. Drinking water facilities available in the rural areas of Purba Medinipur district, 2016-17

Name Of Blocks	Total number of Villages	Tap water	Well water	Hand Pump	Tubewell	Spring	River	Tank/Pond	Others
Tamluk	99	49	10	83	38	0	63	77	3
Sahid Matangini	86	24	3	77	15	0	11	42	3
Panskura	230	33	28	224	67	0	101	206	4
Kolaghat	109	15	4	100	45	0	57	87	0
Moyna	85	8	1	85	30	0	75	81	0
Nandakumar	101	46	0	97	26	0	33	80	1
Mahisadal	75	38	22	56	40	0	33	57	0
Nandigram I	98	5	3	69	41	0	32	75	2
Nandigram II	40	3	1	31	18	0	10	32	1
Chandipur	112	9	0	108	7	0	13	38	1
Sutahata	80	35	4	73	24	0	34	58	2
Haldia	24	3	0	24	0	0	3	24	0
Patashpur I	139	8	3	127	82	0	20	87	0
Patashpur II	151	3	0	142	44	0	37	114	1
Egra I	133	6	2	112	42	0	15	56	0
Egra II	117	19	4	96	83	0	50	95	0
Khejuri I	42	10	0	33	18	0	14	28	0
Khejuri II	99	28	6	44	41	0	28	41	19
Bhagwanpur I	165	25	1	150	60	0	41	100	5
Bhagwanpur II	151	38	1	97	137	0	45	108	1
Ramnagar I	149	17	0	135	40	0	9	81	0
Ramnagar II	137	30	3	115	75	0	21	48	0
Contai I	225	60	3	154	104	0	40	152	2
Deshopran	168	37	0	98	123	0	52	89	1
Contai III	166	55	3	111	33	0	39	99	0

Source: All B.D.O.s, Purba Medinipur, P.A.O., Purba Medinipur, 2019.

Source: As in Table- 1

Fig. 2

Source: As in Table- 1

Fig. 3

The district has a good supply of drinking water. In the four Municipalities ground water constitutes the chief source for drinking purpose and it is supplied by the Municipal authorities by overhead water tanks and pipe line. Water is pumped from underground through deep tubewells. Also in the rural areas underground water is the chief source of drinking water. Fig. 2 shows that most of the mouzas in the Blocks have drinking water facilities from various sources. There are about fifteen Blocks where hundred percent mouzas have been facilitated with safe drinking water. In the rural areas most of the tubewells are of deep tubewell type and are set up by the Panchayats to avail this basic amenity to the people. Tap water facilities are comparatively less available to the villages of the district. Most of the mouzas do not have tap water supply (Fig. 3), they have to rely only on groundwater.

It could be expected that with the Jal Jeevan Mission initiatives, the betterment of life of the mass population would be expected.

Government Initiatives:

Water is largely a state subject. The responsibility of groundwater management, which includes taking initiatives for mitigating the contamination issue and improving groundwater quality, majorly lies with the state governments. Multiple steps however have been undertaken by the Central Government in this regard over the years. The government has implemented distinctive water quality monitoring programs for the purpose of assessing arsenic levels in groundwater and identifying contaminated areas.

To address and manage water pollution, the Central Pollution Control Board (CPCB), in collaboration with State Pollution Control Boards (SPCBs) and Pollution Control Committees (PCCs), has actively enforced the Water (Prevention and Control of Pollution) Act of 1974 and the Environment (Protection) Act of 1986. These legislative frameworks are designed to safeguard water resources by preventing and controlling pollution in both surface and groundwater sources.

In addition to regulatory efforts, the Department of Drinking Water & Sanitation launched the National Water Quality Sub-Mission (NWQSM) under the broader National Rural Drinking Water Programme (NRDWP). This initiative, which is now integrated into the Jal Jeevan Mission (JJM), was specifically aimed at addressing drinking water issues in rural areas that are impacted by arsenic and fluoride contamination. Under this program, a number of mitigation strategies

have been put into place, like deploying arsenic removal technologies and promoting the use of alternative, safe water sources to ensure a reliable supply of clean drinking water.

The Government of India has been implementing the Jal Jeevan Mission (JJM) since the year of 2019, working jointly with state governments to deliver safe, potable tap water of adequate quality to every rural household. This mission puts emphasis on providing a continuous and long-term supply of drinking water, helping to improve the quality of life and health outcomes in rural communities.

On the urban front, the Atal Mission for Rejuvenation and Urban Transformation (AMRUT) was launched in 2015 and covers 500 selected cities and towns across the country. AMRUT focuses on enhancing essential urban infrastructure, including dependable water supply systems, efficient sewerage and septage management, effective stormwater drainage, the creation of green spaces and parks, and the development of pedestrian-friendly urban transport. Building on this, AMRUT 2.0 was introduced in 2021 for the 2021–2026 period. Its primary objective is to achieve universal water supply coverage by ensuring functional household tap connections in statutory towns across India, thereby supporting both sustainability and urban inclusivity.

Groundwater Quality Assessment in Purba Medinipur (2019–2023):

Groundwater forms the backbone of rural and urban water supply in Purba Medinipur, a coastal district in West Bengal. With a significant portion of its population relying on groundwater for drinking, irrigation, and domestic use, the long-term sustainability and safety of this vital resource are of paramount importance. However, the quality of groundwater is increasingly under pressure due to both natural processes and anthropogenic activities, including excessive extraction, agricultural runoff, and saline intrusion from the nearby Bay of Bengal.

This analysis presents a detailed comparative study of groundwater quality in Purba Medinipur over four reference years—2019, 2020, 2022, and 2023. Drawing from measured parameters across multiple administrative blocks and villages, the assessment evaluates the physico-chemical composition of groundwater, including pH, electrical conductivity (EC), total dissolved solids (TDS), major anions (e.g., bicarbonates, chlorides, sulphates), and cations (such as calcium, magnesium, sodium, and potassium). In addition, emerging contaminants like fluoride, iron, and arsenic are critically analyzed due to their known health implications.

Table - 2. Groundwater quality in Purba Medinipur District, 2019

Block	Village	pH	EC in $\mu\text{S/cm}$	CO ₃	HCO ₃	Cl	SO ₄	NO ₃	TH	Ca	Mg	Na	K	F	TDS
Khejuri	Kastala	7.42	1056	0	287	184	10	0.00	175	8	38	156	4	0.00	575
Mahisadal	Chaitanyapur	7.37	1255	0	421	213	62	10	205	34	29	239	5	0.00	849
Nandakumar	Kapasaria	7.27	934	0	293	85	82	21	230	26	40	102	7	0.74	543
Nandigram I	Nandigram	7.40	947	0	177	145	34	22	185	58	10	108	4	0.00	489
Nandigram II	Uttar Boyal	7.48	1216	0	415	191	26	3	170	22	28	208	3	0.30	735
Panskura II	Kolaghat	7.71	745	0	342	78	4	14	140	24	19	115	3	0.30	466
Panskura II	Kolaghat	7.49	1349	0	512	160	52	20	345	56	50	143	31	0.40	824
Potashpur I	Mangal Maro	7.43	841	0	317	103	11	21	235	30	39	79	4	0.40	480
Potashpur I	Patashpur	7.56	518	0	317	18	0.00	0.00	190	42	21	41	3	0.68	318
Potashpur II	Dakshin Kharh	7.55	540	0	232	60	4	3	225	38	32	22	2	0.40	302
Ramnagar II	Dharampur	7.52	571	0	342	32	11	4	225	34	34	46	2	0.00	372

Source: Central Ground Water Board (CGWB), 2019

Table - 3. Groundwater quality in Purba Medinipur District, 2020.

Block	Village	pH	EC in µS/cm	CO ₃	HCO ₃	Cl	SO ₄	NO ₃	TH	Ca	Mg	Na	K	F	TDS
Khejuri	Kastala	7.42	1056	0	287	184	10	0.00	175	8	38	156	4	0.00	575
Mahisadal	Chaitanyapur	7.37	1255	0	421	213	62	10	205	34	29	239	5	0.00	849
Nandakumar	Kapaseria	7.27	934	0	293	85	82	21	230	26	40	102	7	0.74	543
Nandigram I	Nandigram	7.40	947	0	177	145	34	22	185	58	10	108	4	0.00	489
Nandigram II	Uttar Boyal	7.48	1216	0	415	191	26	3	170	22	28	208	3	0.30	735
Panskura II	Kolaghat	7.71	745	0	342	78	4	14	140	24	19	115	3	0.30	466
Panskura II	Kolaghat	7.49	1349	0	512	160	52	20	345	56	50	143	31	0.40	824
Potashpur I	Mangal Maro	7.43	841	0	317	103	11	21	235	30	39	79	4	0.40	480
Potashpur I	Patashpur	7.56	518	0	317	18	0.00	0.00	190	42	21	41	3	0.68	318
Potashpur II	Dakshin Kharh	7.55	540	0	232	60	4	3	225	38	32	22	2	0.40	302
Ramnagar II	Dharampur	7.52	571	0	342	32	11	4	225	34	34	46	2	0.00	372

Source: Central Ground Water Board (CGWB), 2020

Table - 4. Groundwater quality in Purba Medinipur District, 2022

Block	Village	pH	EC	CO ₃	HCO ₃	Cl	SO ₄	NO ₃	PO ₄	TH	Ca	Mg	Na	K	F	U _p pb
Panskura-II	Kolaghat	6.93	1260	0	518.5	134.7	0.0	0.0	0	370	80.0	41.3	116.8	40.3	0.03	0
Potashpur-I	Potashpur P.S	7.83	183.8	0	109.8	17.7	1.5	0.1	0	70	18.0	6.1	10.1	1.2	0.90	0
Potashpur-I	Potashpur PHC	7.8	585.7	0	366.0	35.5	0.0	0.0	0	225	46.0	26.7	44.0	1.4	0.05	0
Mayna	Dakshin Anukha Gram	7.97	431.6	0	152.5	60.3	0.0	0.0	0	100	18.0	13.3	41.1	16.3	0.23	0
Potashpur-II	Pratapdighi	8.48	305.2	0	183.0	17.7	0.0	0.0	0	110	40.0	2.4	13.9	1.4	0.16	0
Potashpur-I	Mangla Maro	7.74	582.6	0	366.0	28.4	0.0	0.0	0	175	34.0	21.8	61.0	2.1	0.39	0
Panskura-II	Kolaghat	8.08	351.5	0	183.0	39.0	0.0	0.0	0	170	32.0	21.8	22.1	3.2	0.04	0
Ramnagar -I	Sankarpur (DEW PHE)	7.77	736	0	402.6	49.6	0.0	0.0	0	310	26.0	59.5	77.4	5.2	0.10	0
Mahisadal	Chaitanyap ur DEW	7.96	898.3	0	396.5	99.3	0.0	0.0	0	220	18.0	42.5	104.1	3.8	0.30	0
Ramnagar -II	Dharambur i	7.86	1323	0	427.0	216.2	0.0	0.1	0	280	54.0	35.2	124.5	36.7	0.14	0
Bhagwanp ur-I	Kishorpur	8.17	770.8	0	311.1	117.0	21.6	0.0	0	285	36.0	47.3	62.1	2.9	0.32	0
Ramnagar -I	Nimtala	7.4	1297	0	390.4	237.5	0.0	0.0	0	235	38.0	34.0	116.5	28.9	0.10	0
Ramnagar -II	Dadan Patrabarh	8.08	576.7	0	366.0	21.3	4.9	0.0	0	175	38.0	19.4	56.1	4.4	0.32	0
Potashpur -II	Dakshin Kharh	8	844.2	0	353.8	117.0	0.0	0.0	0	220	36.0	31.6	84.5	6.1	0.07	0
Khejuri-II	Sher Khan Chak	8.29	556.7	0	280.6	49.6	2.0	0.1	0	230	52.0	24.3	27.4	2.6	0.00	0
Khejuri-II	Khejuri	7.7	1233	0	158.6	209.2	0.0	0.0	0	250	36.0	38.8	124.5	30.4	0.44	0
Sutahata	Haldia	8.48	315.5	0	231.8	24.8	0.0	0.0	0	165	24.0	25.5	12.6	2.4	0.04	0

Source: Central Ground Water Board (CGWB), 2020

Table - 5. Groundwater quality in Purba Medinipur District, 2023

Village	pH	EC (µS/cm at)	CO ₃ (mg/L)	HCO ₃ (mg/L)	Cl (mg/L)	F (mg/L)	SO ₄	NO ₃	PO ₄	Total Hardness	Ca (mg/L)	Mg (mg/L)	Na (mg/L)	K (mg/L)	Fe (ppm)	As (ppb)
Kishorpur	7.53	558	0	329	21	0.19	0	0	0.00	160	40	15	64	3	0.30	1.16
Bhupatinagar ugberia Gramin	7.21	923	0	348	170	0.12	0	0	0.00	160	20	27	148	4	0.80	0.00
Contai 1 BDO Office	7.13	539	0	207	39	0.06	36	4	0.00	205	60	13	39	5	1.10	0.00
Bonamali Chhadha	6.92	1011	0	317	184	0.12	0	0	0.00	215	30	34	154	4	0.80	2.42
Panchayet Samiti Office	7.68	1103	0	390	199	0.17	0	0	0.00	295	50	41	117	4	0.30	0.00
Kudi	7.46	320	0	207	18	0.18	0	0	0.00	145	28	18	14	1	0.30	0.00
Bhawanichak	7.25	408	0	268	18	0.08	0	0	0.00	115	18	17	48	3	1.80	0.00
Sbstc Haldia Bus Stand	7.36	941	0	268	195	0.14	0	0	0.00	200	26	33	139	4	0.90	0.00
Kastala	7.15	966	0	390	177	0.13	0	1	0.00	160	22	26	160	5	2.70	0.00
Nijkashba	7.28	879	0	366	128	0.14	0	1	0.00	170	18	30	134	5	0.90	0.00
Ramchak	6.93	1042	0	372	206	0.14	0	0	0.00	180	24	29	162	4	0.70	0.00
Khejuri	6.96	797	0	378	96	0.13	0	1	0.00	160	18	28	117	4	0.60	0.00
Ramchak	7.63	915	0	378	135	0.17	0	0	0.00	205	44	23	112	4	0.90	0.00
Sher Khan Chak	7.15	1099	0	378	220	0.12	0	0	0.00	250	52	29	145	4	1.20	0.00
Chaitanyapur Dew	7.12	1154	0	390	220	0.13	0	0	0.00	220	50	23	179	4	0.50	0.00
Mayna (Gar Safat)	7.78	668	0	366	71	0.18	0	4	0.00	150	30	18	97	3	0.30	3.27
Uttar Boyal	7.25	1010	0	366	191	0.15	0	0	0.00	150	24	22	179	4	0.60	0.00
Kolaghat	7.41	711	0	366	46	0.31	0	0	0.00	150	32	17	105	3	1.10	0.00
Kolaghat	7.07	1086	0	427	85	0.52	51	26	0.00	320	82	28	112	23	0.70	0.00
Brajajalpur Singda	7.94	429	0	275	18	0.32	0	0	0.00	105	18	15	55	1	0.60	0.00
Mangla Maro	7.57	1659	0	305	404	0.16	0	0	0.00	425	46	75	204	3	0.60	0.00
Potashpur P.S	7.93	454	0	281	32	0.30	0	0	0.00	150	26	21	43	2	0.90	0.00
Potashpur Phc	7.88	520	0	299	50	0.25	0	0	0.00	145	30	17	61	2	0.70	4.27
Dakshin Kharh	7.30	427	0	238	43	0.28	0	2	0.00	190	34	26	19	1	0.40	0.00
Pratapdighi	7.85	687	0	293	89	0.25	0	0	0.00	185	30	27	86	2	3.30	0.00
Digha	7.09	489	0	305	35	0.10	0	0	0.00	125	20	18	64	3	0.70	0.00
Nimtala	7.15	516	0	372	7	0.16	0	0	0.00	160	28	22	55	3	12.90	0.00
Sankarpur (Dew Phe)	6.99	700	0	342	89	0.16	0	0	0.00	150	18	26	101	3	0.60	0.00
Dadan Patrabarh	6.96	687	0	299	43	0.11	24	6	0.00	170	26	26	91	4	3.10	0.00
Dharamburi	7.28	1534	0	256	386	0.19	0	0	0.00	470	46	86	148	3	0.60	0.00
Jinandapur	7.04	425	0	250	21	0.09	0	0	0.00	125	18	19	47	3	0.80	0.00
Baluaghata	7.21	1180	0	390	248	0.22	0	0	0.00	135	26	17	216	3	0.40	0.00
Haldia	7.05	2166	0	439	486	0.44	0	10	0.00	445	68	67	280	75	0.30	1.18
Harkhali	7.15	951	0	366	177	0.16	0	0	0.00	130	22	18	168	3	0.40	0.00
Tamluk	7.41	875	0	372	99	0.13	0	0	0.00	190	34	26	117	4	0.40	2.02

Source: Central Ground Water Board (CGWB), 2023

Key Parameters Considered

pH – water acidity/alkalinity

EC (µS/cm) – electrical conductivity, indicating ion concentration

HCO₃, Cl, SO₄, NO₃ – major anions

TH (Total Hardness), Ca, Mg, Na, K – hardness and major cations

F – fluoride content

TDS – total dissolved solids

Fe, As (only 2023) – heavy metals

Observations and Trends

pH

1. Mostly neutral to slightly alkaline (6.9–8.4).
2. Slight drop in Khejuri and Nandigram blocks in 2023.
3. Notably high in Potashpur II and Bhagwanpur (8.17–8.48).

EC (µS/cm)

1. Generally increased in many locations in 2023, indicating higher ionic concentration.
2. Example: Mangla Maro EC rose from 841 → 1659, suggesting significant mineral dissolution or contamination.

TDS

1. Available only for 2019–2022 datasets.
2. Highest TDS: Chaitanyapur (849), Kolaghat (824).
3. Suggests moderate to poor drinking quality in these locations.

Chloride (Cl)

1. Fluctuating trends. Notable spikes:
2. Mangla Maro: from 103 → 404 (2023)
3. Dharamburi: 216.2 (2022) → 386 (2023)

Fluoride (F)

1. Below WHO guideline (1.5 mg/L) in most areas.
2. Rising trend in some blocks like Kolaghat and Nimtala in 2023 (up to 0.52 and 0.16 respectively).
3. Exception: Nimtala in 2023 with a fluoride level of 12.9 mg/L – extremely unsafe.

Total Hardness (TH)

1. Marked increase in 2023 in some villages like Mangla Maro (425), Kolaghat (320), and Dharamburi (470), indicating very hard water.
2. Sodium (Na)
3. Sodium levels rose sharply in some blocks like Mangla Maro (204 mg/L), indicating salinity risks.
4. Khejuri, Kolaghat, and Chaitanyapur also showed consistently high sodium.
5. New Parameters in 2023
6. Iron (Fe): Generally low (0.1–1.2 ppm), but above permissible limits in some areas (e.g., Nimtala – 12.9 ppm).
7. Arsenic (As): Mostly absent or minimal. Detected at 1.16 ppb in Kishorpur, below WHO limit.

One of the most consistent observations is the stability in pH values, which generally hover between 6.9 and 8.4. This indicates that the groundwater remains neutral to slightly alkaline across most locations, which is favorable for both agricultural and domestic usage. However, slight acidification trends in Khejuri and Kolaghat in 2023 suggest potential geochemical shifts or contamination influences that should be watched.

One of the most alarming findings comes from fluoride analysis. While fluoride was virtually absent in the 2019 and 2022 datasets, its sudden appearance and drastic elevation in 2023, particularly in Nimtala (12.9 mg/L), represent a serious public health hazard. The World Health Organization's permissible limit for fluoride in drinking water is 1.5 mg/L, and levels such as those recorded in Nimtala are known to cause severe skeletal and dental fluorosis. This requires immediate remediation through treatment technologies and public health advisories.

Heavy metals such as iron have also begun to appear more frequently, with levels exceeding the IS:10500 aesthetic threshold (0.3 mg/L) in locations like Bonamali Chhadha, Bhawanichak, and Nimtala. While arsenic levels remain negligible overall, its detection in trace amounts in select locations like Kishorpur warrants continued vigilance, especially given the district's proximity to arsenic-prone regions.

It can be said that, while the groundwater in Purba Medinipur remains usable in many areas, there is clear evidence of localized degradation—primarily due to rising salinity, hardness, and fluoride content. These emerging threats, if left unaddressed, could severely compromise both public health and the long-term sustainability of groundwater as a resource. A combination of robust monitoring, decentralized water treatment interventions, alternative source development, and community awareness initiatives is essential to mitigate these risks and ensure safe water access for future generations.

Challenges to combat:

The persistent contamination of water sources by arsenic and fluoride continues to be a significant health and environmental concern in many parts of India, especially in states like West Bengal. In several regions of West Bengal, the concentration of fluoride in drinking water far exceeds the permissible safety limits, posing a serious risk to public health.

Arsenic and fluoride are both particularly dangerous because they are silent contaminants—colorless, odorless, and tasteless—which makes their presence in water nearly impossible to detect without scientific testing. Their long-term consumption can lead to devastating health consequences. For instance, skeletal fluorosis caused by excessive fluoride intake can result in chronic pain and immobility. These contaminants affect individuals quietly but relentlessly, degrading health and livelihoods over time. What makes this situation particularly tragic is that both arsenic and fluoride-related health issues are preventable if identified early. The key lies in timely surveillance, accurate detection, and the implementation of comprehensive prevention and treatment strategies.

Beyond water contamination, another looming crisis is the impact of climate change, which further complicates efforts to provide safe drinking water. The Sundarbans region, for instance, faces persistent threats of flooding and intrusion of saline water, making freshwater scarce and exacerbating the contamination issue. In a similar manner, in Birbhum, which is characterized by laterite soil, droughts are becoming increasingly frequent due to shifting climate patterns. These changes have also led to more intense and erratic rainfall, resulting in excessive runoff or flooding in some areas, which further disrupts local water supplies and infrastructure.

A major part of the solution involves the development and maintenance of quality infrastructure that is manageable by local communities. Effective water resource management must ensure that water intended for drinking, cooking, and sanitation does not get contaminated by wastewater or other harmful sources. However, building and maintaining infrastructure at a scale large enough to meet the needs of growing populations in remote and underserved areas is a significant logistical and operational challenge. Even when systems are put in place, maintaining them to ensure consistent service delivery is a formidable task, particularly when technical support and resources are limited.

Infrastructure-related constraints are compounded by financial limitations. There are many rural and arsenic-affected regions that lack the funds necessary to implement and sustain water purification technologies. This financial shortfall makes it extremely difficult to scale up solutions that could benefit large populations. Moreover, the access to the right technologies adds another layer of complexity. Arsenic mitigation techniques that work well in one hydrogeological region may not be effective in another, making it essential to tailor solutions to specific local conditions. Once these technologies are deployed, they require regular maintenance and trained personnel to operate them. Unfortunately, in many communities, the technical expertise or funding required for such upkeep is often lacking.

Another critical challenge is the general lack of awareness and education about the dangers of arsenic and fluoride contamination. Without widespread knowledge, communities may not fully participate in or support mitigation efforts. Public health campaigns and education initiatives are essential to empower people with the information they need to take proactive steps.

Population growth in affected areas is placing increasing pressure on existing water supply systems. As more people require access to clean water, the demand often exceeds the capacity of infrastructure that may already be failing or contaminated. Climate change also contributes to hydrogeological changes, altering the way arsenic moves through groundwater and making it harder to manage contamination using existing strategies.

These issues are creating significant obstacles for the Indian government's Jal Jeevan Mission, which aims to provide safe tap water to every rural household. A government assessment has revealed that over 56,000 rural households across 18 states currently receive water tainted with harmful contaminants such as fluoride, arsenic, iron, salinity, nitrate, and other heavy metals. The states of West Bengal, Rajasthan, and Assam are among the most severely affected. The Ministry of Jal Shakti, in a submission to the parliamentary standing committee on water resources, acknowledged that groundwater contamination poses one of the greatest challenges to achieving the mission's ambitious targets. Without addressing these multifaceted problems, the goal of universal access to safe drinking water will remain out of reach for millions.

Initiatives under Jal Jeevan Mission:

The Government of India, in collaboration with various State and Union Territory (UT) administrations, has been executing the Jal Jeevan Mission (JJM) – Har Ghar Jal since August 2019. This ambitious program is designed with the primary objective of ensuring that every rural household across the country receives a

dependable and continuous supply of potable tap water. The supply must meet specific quality standards and be adequate in quantity, thus enabling a long-term and sustainable water distribution infrastructure. The **Jal Jeevan Mission** is transforming rural India by ensuring access to safe tap water for over 81% of households in just six years.

To maintain the quality of drinking water provided under the mission, the Government has adopted the Bureau of Indian Standards (BIS) guideline BIS:10500, which outlines the prescribed norms for safe and acceptable tap water quality. This standard serves as the national benchmark for delivering safe drinking water to rural homes and is central to JJM's implementation strategy.

In terms of financial allocation, the JJM guidelines mandate that 10% of the funds distributed to States and UTs must take into account the population living in regions affected by chemical contamination in water. These chemical contaminants include dangerous elements like arsenic and fluoride, which pose serious health hazards. Giving this weightage makes sure that the areas most in need receive appropriate financial and technical support.

Further, States and Union Territories have been directed to design and implement piped water supply schemes based on bulk water transfer systems, preferably utilizing surface water sources. In cases where surface water is not feasible, alternative safe groundwater sources are to be considered. This directive is especially important for villages that are facing persistent water quality challenges, such as high arsenic content.

Jal Jeevan Mission also emphasizes the need to prioritize areas where water contamination is most severe. During the planning phase of water supply systems, special attention is given to these quality-affected habitations. As a temporary measure, until piped water systems are fully operational, States and UTs are encouraged to install Community Water Purification Plants (CWPPs). These plants are particularly vital in regions affected by arsenic and fluoride, and they are tasked with providing 8–10 litres per capita per day of purified water per household, enough to meet basic drinking and cooking needs.

To facilitate the monitoring and testing of water quality across the country, the government introduced the "Drinking Water Quality Monitoring & Surveillance Framework" in October 2021. This framework provides a structured approach for tracking water quality, enabling both proactive and reactive measures to be taken by concerned authorities.

Recognizing the importance of scientific research in addressing water contamination, the Ministry has funded several research projects, particularly those related to the mitigation of arsenic and other toxic substances in groundwater. Many of these studies are conducted in collaboration with institutions such as the Geological Survey of India (GSI). The outcomes of these research initiatives are shared with implementing agencies and the public to ensure awareness and effective policy decisions.

A range of technological initiatives have also been rolled out to tackle groundwater contamination. These efforts are increasingly community-centric, acknowledging that involving local communities is crucial for long-term success. Here are some of the key steps taken under JJM:

1. **Establishment of Water Quality Testing Laboratories:** More than 2,000 laboratories have been set up across the country to support comprehensive water testing. Additionally, in each village, five individuals—preferably women—are selected and trained to use Field Test Kits (FTKs) to test local water samples. This community-based testing approach not only empowers locals but also enables real-time quality assessment.
2. **Development of the Water Quality Management Information System (WQMIS):** An online portal has been created under JJM to help States and UTs manage tasks such as water sample collection, quality testing, data reporting, and surveillance. This digital tool is instrumental in improving transparency and efficiency in monitoring drinking water quality.
3. **Creation of the National Centre for Drinking Water, Sanitation and Quality (NCDWSQ):** This is an autonomous institution under the Department of Drinking Water & Sanitation, Ministry of Jal Shakti. It focuses on identifying, managing, and mitigating problems related to drinking water quality across both rural and urban settings. It specifically focuses on harmful contaminants like arsenic and fluoride.
4. **Arsenic-Free Well Construction Technology:** The Central Ground Water Board (CGWB) has developed an innovative method for constructing wells that tap into deeper, uncontaminated aquifers. This technique is shared with

state-level agencies, enabling them to replicate the method and expand the number of arsenic-free wells in affected areas.

5. **Public Awareness Campaigns and Groundwater Education:** The CGWB conducts regular Public Interaction Programmes (PIPs) to educate communities about groundwater contamination, safe water usage practices, and pollution prevention. These grassroots-level awareness initiatives are vital for changing behaviors and ensuring the sustainability of clean water efforts.

Nationwide Groundwater Monitoring by CGWB: The CGWB undertakes regular assessments of groundwater quality across the country. These evaluations cover a wide range of contaminants, including arsenic, and are conducted both on a routine basis and through special scientific studies. The findings are made publicly available via official reports and the CGWB's website. Moreover, this data is routinely shared with State Governments to support informed policymaking and remediation actions.

The Jal Jeevan Mission (JJM) was launched nationwide by the Government of India on August 15, 2019, with the goal of providing a functional household tap connection to every rural household. In West Bengal, the state government launched its implementation of the mission, which it renamed as 'Jal Swapno', in July 2020, instead of August 2019 when the central scheme began. Purba Medinipur district falls under this statewide implementation, with specific project activities and the engagement of implementation support agencies in various blocks (such as Tamluk, Kolaghat, Panskura) being documented from 2023 onwards as implementation progressed. Therefore, the mission's operations began in the Purba Medinipur district as part of the state's rollout starting in July 2020.

The Purba Medinipur district implements Jal Jeevan Mission (JJM) schemes focused on providing Functional Household Tap Connections (FHTC) to every rural home. Key activities include implementing piped water supply schemes in various blocks, like the "SANTIPUR and ADJOINING MOUZAS" scheme in Sahid Matangini block, and retrofitting existing schemes to connect more households. The mission also involves engaging Implementation Support Agencies (ISAs) for project implementation and supervision, as well as monitoring water quality in the district.

Key scheme activities in Purba Medinipur District

Piped water supply schemes: The district is undertaking new piped water supply schemes to connect homes (Fig. 4). An example is the "SANTIPUR and ADJOINING MOUZAS, Block Shahid Matangini" scheme, which includes the installation of submersible pumps and other equipment.

Retrofitting existing schemes: Existing water supply schemes are being retrofitted to accommodate more households and provide tap connections under the JJM program.

Implementation Support Agencies (ISAs): The district engages ISAs to assist with the implementation of JJM in various blocks, including Tamluk, Kolaghat, Panskura, Sahid Matangini, Bhagwanpur, Khejuri, Egra, and Contai.

Monitoring and supervision: The Public Health Engineering (PHE) Department of the district hires inspection vehicles for monitoring the progress of ongoing piped water supply schemes.

Water quality monitoring: Water quality is monitored through various tests, and data is collected to ensure the water supplied is of prescribed quality.

Source: wbphed.gov.in, Nov 2025.

Fig. 4

The rural areas (Fig. 4) in the Blocks of Purba Medinipur district are actively implementing the [Jal Jeevan Mission](#), with various ongoing projects including laying pipelines, installing submersible pumps, and hiring vehicles for supervision throughout the district.

Conclusion

Comprehensive plans and their systematic implementation are necessary to reduce the discharge of harmful metals into the groundwater, and ensure healthy living across West Bengal. Strict monitoring and regulations, avoiding groundwater usage without proper treatment, social awareness campaigns and safe recharge of groundwater can help minimize the health hazards in the region. Government and non-governmental organizations need to carry out awareness campaigns and health education programs to inform communities about the risks associated with arsenic-contaminated water and promote safe water practices in the region. Involving local communities in the process of decision making, as well as encouraging the adoption of safe water practices are also essential components of arsenic mitigation efforts.

In addition to demanding accountability from the government, common people need to also collaborate with relevant stakeholders whenever possible in order to do their bit. Addressing the challenges of arsenic contamination in West Bengal's ground water requires a holistic and multidimensional approach, which involves collaboration between governments, non-governmental organizations, communities, and the scientific community.

References

1. Banerjee, P., Mukherjee, A., & Singh, R. (2019). Fluoride occurrence in groundwater of eastern India and associated health risks. *Environmental*

- Earth Sciences, 78(14), pp 1–12, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12665-019-8452-6>
2. Central Ground Water Board. (2020). Groundwater quality in shallow aquifers of India, Ministry of Jal Shakti, Government of India, pp 45-78.
 3. Central Ground Water Board. (2022). Groundwater year book of West Bengal 2021–22, Ministry of Jal Shakti, Government of India, pp 12-39.
 4. Chakraborti, D., Rahman, M. M., Mukherjee, A., Alauddin, M., & Ahmed, K. M. (2015). Groundwater arsenic contamination in the Ganga–Meghna–Brahmaputra Plain. *Journal of Hazardous Materials*, 262, 915–924. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2013.10.016>
 5. Chakraborty, S., & Ghosh, A. (2022). Impact of coastal aquaculture on groundwater salinity in eastern India. *Journal of Coastal Conservation*, 26(3), pp 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11852-022-00857-4>
 6. Chandna, R.C. (2000), *Geography Of Population*, Kalyani Publishers, Calcutta, p. 2, p. 32, p. 208, p. 210, p. 215, p. 242, p. 255, p. 261.
 7. Das, S., Ghosh, P., & Saha, D. (2017). Hydrochemical assessment of coastal aquifers of West Bengal. *Environmental Monitoring and Assessment*, 189(8), 395–410. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10661-017-6115-4>
 8. Ghosh, S., & Biswas, M. (2021). Groundwater quality assessment in coastal districts of West Bengal, India. *Journal of Water and Climate Change*, 12(5), 1564–1578. <https://doi.org/10.2166/wcc.2021.210>
 9. Hoque MM, Hossen MA, Zuthi MFR, Mullick MRA, Hasan SMF, Khan F, Das T. Exploration of trace elements in groundwater and associated human health risk in Chattogram City of Bangladesh. *Heliyon*. 2024 Aug 2;10(15):e35738. doi: 10.1016/j.heliyon.2024.e35738. PMID: 39170401; PMCID: PMC11336830.
 10. Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change. (2021). *Climate change 2021: The physical science basis*, Cambridge University Press, pp 1213-1289.
 11. Khosla, R.K. (2000), *Rural and Urban development In India*, Indian Publishers and Distributors, New Delhi, pp. 10-11.
 12. Kumar, M., Ramanathan, A. L., Rao, M. S., & Kumar, B. (2020). Seasonal dynamics of groundwater quality in eastern India. *Journal of Hydrology*, 582, 124522–124534. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhydrol.2019.124522>
 13. Liu F., Song X., Yang L., et al. The role of anthropogenic and natural factors in shaping the geochemical evolution of groundwater in the Subei Lake basin, Ordos energy base, Northwestern China. *Sci. Total Environ*. 2015;538:327–340. doi: 10.1016/j.scitotenv.2015.08.057. [DOI] [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
 14. Meinzen-Dick, R. (2014). Groundwater governance: Conceptual framework. *Water International*, 39(3), pp 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02508060.2014.903453>
 15. Malley, L.S.S.O'. (Reprint 1995), *Bengal District Gazetteers*, Midnapore, West Bengal District Gazetteers, Government of West Bengal, Calcutta, pp. 58-67.
 16. Meinzen-Dick, R. (2014). Groundwater governance: Conceptual framework. *Water International*, 39(3), pp 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02508060.2014.903453>
 17. Mukherjee, A., Fryar, A. E., & Scanlon, B. R. (2020). Regional groundwater flow and contamination in coastal aquifers of eastern India. *Hydrogeology Journal*, 28(5), 1601–1616. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10040-020-02158-9>
 18. Mukherji, A., Shah, T., & Giordano, M. (2019). Groundwater governance in South Asia, *International Water Management Institute*, pp 67-102.
 19. Opoku P.A., Anornu G.K., Gibrilla A., et al. Spatial distributions and probabilistic risk assessment of exposure to heavy metals in groundwater in a peri-urban settlement: case study of Atonsu-Kumasi, Ghana. *Groundw. Sustain. Dev*. 2020;10
 20. Roy, S., Saha, D., & Ghosh, S. (2016). Iron contamination in groundwater of West Bengal: Hydrogeochemical perspective. *Environmental Earth Sciences*, 75(7), 543–556. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12665-016-5342-3>
 21. Sarkar A, Paul B, Darbha GK. The groundwater arsenic contamination in the Bengal Basin-A review in brief. *Chemosphere*. 2022 July;299:134369. doi: 10.1016/j.chemosphere.2022.134369. Epub 2022 Mar 19. PMID: 35318018.
 22. Saha, D., Dhar, Y. R., & Sikdar, P. K. (2018). Salinity intrusion in coastal aquifers of India. *Current Science*, 114(4), pp 791–799.
 23. Selvam S., Antony Ravindran A., Venkatramanan S., et al. Assessment of heavy metal and bacterial pollution in coastal aquifers from SIPCOT industrial zones, Gulf of Mannar, South Coast of Tamil Nadu, India. *Appl. Water Sci*. 2017;7(2):897–913. [Google Scholar]
 24. Sharma R., Kumar R., Agrawal P.R., et al. *Water Conservation in the Era of Global Climate Change*. Elsevier; 2021. Groundwater extractions and climate change; pp. 23–45. [Google Scholar]

25. Thirlwall, A.P. (1994), *Growth and Development, fifth Edition*, MacMillan Press Ltd, London, p. 143.
26. Tyagi, Nutan (2006), *Quality Of Life of Industrial Workers: A Case Study of Gorakhpur Region*, *Indian Journal of Landscape System and Ecological Studies*, Institute of Landscape, Ecology and Ekistics, Kolkata, Vol.29 (1), June, 2006, pp. 82-84.
27. UN-Water. (2018). *Sustainable Development Goal 6 synthesis report*, United Nations, pp 11-28.
28. UN-Water. (2023). *Progress on freshwater ecosystems*, United Nations, pp 43-66.
29. Vetrinurugan E., Brindha K., Elango L., et al. *Human exposure risk to heavy metals through groundwater used for drinking in an intensively irrigated river delta*. *Appl. Water Sci.* 2017;7(6):3267–3280.
30. World Health Organization. (2017). *Guidelines for drinking-water quality*, 4th ed., WHO Press, pp 201-276.
31. Xiao J., Wang L., Chai N., Liu T., et al. *Groundwater hydrochemistry, source identification and pollution assessment in intensive industrial areas, eastern Chinese loess plateau*. *Environ. Pollut.* 2021;278 doi: 10.1016/j.envpol.2021.116930. [DOI] [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
32. <https://jaljeevanmission.gov.in/sites/default/files/guideline/SubMission%20guidelines.pdf>
33. <https://pib.gov.in/PressReleaselframePage.aspx?PRID=1987662>
34. <https://www.clearias.com/arsenic-contamination-in-india/>
35. <https://www.dailypioneer.com/2024/india/centre-reveals-west-bengal-and-bihar-as-worst-hit-by-arsenic-contamination-of-groundwater.html>
36. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0045653522008621>
37. <https://www.thehindu.com/news/national/west-bengal-bihar-most-impacted-by-arsenic-contamination-centre-tells-ngt/article69015247.ece>